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HEYDAR ALIYEV PHENOMENON IN AZERBAIJANI CULTURE

Abstract. Loving Heydar Aliyev and supporting his political line have serious principles and deep layers. This can be seen more clearly during scientific research. I received my higher education during the Soviet period. Culture was taught within the framework of propaganda and agitation activities as a cultural and educational work at that time. I was engaged in scientific research during Heydar Aliyev's leadership. Theoretical foundations of culture from a conceptual point of view were created during this period. An encyclopedic dictionary, which was published in 1997, gave a practical definition of culture: "It is a social, progressive and creative activity, which consists of the dialectical unity of the objectification and deobjectification processes of humanity in all areas of existence and consciousness, the transformation of reality, the transformation of human historical richness into the inner richness of the personality, and the discovery of the essential forces of human" [3]. The concept of culture and the priorities of cultural policy were defined based on this scientific and theoretical justification. The priority of human and society, which is the subject of culture, manifested. A science – culturology was born, which reveals the creative life of a human, its essence, development laws and transformative possibilities. Human capital: processes of turning natural resources into national wealth become relevant. Naturally, this increased cultural experts' love for Heydar Aliyev. It's impossible not to love a person who cares more about your favorite profession than you do. There is no doubt that the National Leader earned this love in all fields of science. In other words, what endeared Heydar Aliyev to the people was his sincerity,

honesty and supporting them, and what endeared him to intellectuals was his high and deep intellect.

Key words: cultural construction, national and moral values, management culture, cultural and creative elite, public service

Introduction. ANAS is a temple of science distinguished by its loyalty to the legacy of Heydar Aliyev. The memory of the National Leader and his sacrifices in the direction of the development of modern Azerbaijan have always been inspired by the management of the Academy as a subject of scientific thought. Especially, academician Isa Habibbeyli's recommendations regarding the research and promotion of Heydar Aliyev's legacy are among the factors that stimulate scientific research.

Heydar Aliyev's attitude towards Azerbaijani art and art critics as a whole has always been appreciated highly by the leading experts in this field. ANAS Institute of Architecture and Art organizes birthday and commemoration days of the National Leader at a high level every year, and tries to express moral obligations by commemorating the Great Leader's attention and care in this area with pleasant memories and feelings of satisfaction.

Artegin Salamzade, general director of the Institute of Architecture and Art of ANAS, correspondent member of ANAS, takes into account the wishes and desires of art critics at these events, and keeps the event more interesting by determining the number and composition of presentations on different types of art. There are still many ideas to be written and said about Heydar Aliyev. At the same time, professor Artegin Salamzadeh and associate professor Khazar Zeynalov's book "The image of Heydar Aliyev in fine arts", which was published in 2019 and dedicated to the 50th anniversary of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev's being in political power, is a work of great importance in terms of scientific and theoretical evaluations. The events held at the Institute and the works related to the research and promotion of Heydar Aliyev's heritage have a great educational role in the direction of respect for Heydar Aliyev's heritage among young art critics. From this point of view, the research work "Heydar Aliyev phenomenon in Azerbaijani culture", which was prepared in the department of "Culturology and theory of art" of the Institute, can be considered as a continuation of this sacred work.

The interpretation of the main material. The main purpose of the research is to provide a scientific, comparative and critical analysis of the

cultural policy, emphasizing the role played by the Heydar Aliyev phenomenon in the cultural construction, the development of the cultural elite and creative industries of our country, and to investigate the role of this policy in the development of our national and moral values. The goals and tasks set in the direction of determining the role and place of the new cultural policy in the development of our national and moral values and protecting it from etching in contact with the negative manifestations of the globalization process in culture are the main ones in the research.

At the same time, the free functioning of various political parties and public organizations, the free emergence of numerous media outlets, the broadcasting of programs by private television and radio channels, etc. in the republic where Heydar Aliyev preferred political culture are obvious results of the political pluralism, freedom of thought, and democracy prevailing in Azerbaijan. Freedom of conscience and speech, inviolability of personality, provision of basic human and civil rights and freedoms, establishment of an environment of tolerance are among the necessary steps that form a real civil society.

Heydar Aliyev, who guided the unity of the people and the state in political culture, was one of the personalities who realized the famous Turkologist Ziya Gogalp's expression "Toward the people" in his practical activities [4, p.50]. Besides spreading science and culture among his people, he was an example of conveying the national spirit of the people to the intellectuals. Anyone could easily understand any idea from his speeches. Heydar Aliyev could communicate with the leaders of the world's leading countries and the farmer of a remote mountain village in a language that could satisfy the interlocutor. This was one of the qualities that distinguished him, and that not everyone has.

For this purpose, the following tasks have been set and investigated in the research work:

- To study about the events that happened in our culture, the achieved successes, the existing problems and how to overcome them under the leadership of the National Leader after Azerbaijan gained independence;
- To learn the methods of creating, systematizing and improving legislative provision as a builder of cultural policy and political culture, which are important for the development of every state;
- To show the priority of protecting the national and moral values that the Great Leader valued as a part of universal values, to highlight the services

in the formation of the creative elite, the issues of reorganization and development of cultural and creative industries [1, p. 21-22].

The scientific novelty of the research can be classified as following:

- Heydar Aliyev’s work in the formation of the cultural policy of Azerbaijan, the culturological essence of the cultural policy in terms of social goals and moral values have been involved in the study, and the issues of planning and legislative provision in the field of culture have been interpreted;
- The National Leader’s support in solving the problems of the difficulties faced by the state cultural policy, manifestations of political and economic system changes in the field of culture, the work of cultural institutions, the population’s participation in the cultural life, supporting creativity, financing culture and protecting national and moral values in the first years of our independence have been studied within the framework of scientific criteria;
- Special attention has been paid to the prospects of effectiveness and efficiency of the cultural policy founded by Heydar Aliyev and the priority of the policy aimed at the transformation of natural resources into national wealth – human capital, evaluation and understanding of culture as a factor of human development is shown;
- The achievements of the Azerbaijan in the field of cultural policy and its prospects for success, activities related to the protection of cultural industries – creative industries (CI) and national-spiritual heritage have been reviewed, the formation of the cultural elite, and its successes in the cultural and political-ideological field have been evaluated;
- A culturological analysis of the factors determining the formula of a cultured person as the image of a cultured person in culturological studies such as knowledge, skills, self-discipline, spirituality and creative activity in National Leader Heydar Aliyev’s socio-cultural and political work is given [1, p. 23-24].

As a whole, independent Azerbaijan, of which Heydar Aliyev was the founder, can be shown as his creative work. Building a state is not an easy task. What is more difficult than building the state is to ensure its stability and solidity. Heydar Aliyev managed to do both. And, this is the greatest creative work. Of course, he was able to create such a great and powerful work – the modern Republic of Azerbaijan – due to his high qualities such as knowledge, skill, self-discipline and spirituality. It is obvious that cultured people who are

growing up in Heydar Aliyev's example can achieve great ideals. There are concrete and important tasks that are desired to be realized ahead. So, Heydar Aliyev phenomenon can play the role of a light that directs every Azerbaijani youth to high ideals.

Thus, Heydar Aliyev challenged the politics of culture by establishing cultural policy and political culture in the country. Creative elite was formed and the influence of intellectuals on cultural processes expanded. Manifestations of Heydar Aliyev phenomenon were formed in Azerbaijani culture.

Phenomenon (phainomenon in Greek – manifesting, appearing, coming to light) is a concept that expresses an occasion given to us in experience and understood with the help of senses. Husserl, the founder of the phenomenology trend, believed that essence is perceived through phenomena. In this sense, the study of Heydar Aliyev phenomenon can lead to the understanding of the essence of Azerbaijani culture. Heydar Aliyev phenomenon – his works – manifested, revealed cultural events express the essence of Azerbaijani culture. The success of this essence is obvious and can be felt every day.

Conclusion. It was the National Leader's greatest desire to convey what he created to the future generations in a safe and secure way, to see his people always happy and prosperous. Cultural and creative elite had to be formed for this. It should also be mentioned that the talents of the sensitive elite: except technical sciences, many composers, artists, choreographers, architects, actors and directors in the main fields of art left the country in the first years of our independence. The most important thing to be done was to prevent the departure of intellectuals who grew up for many years due to the socio-economic and political crisis characteristic of the transitional period, and in most cases, the "brain drain" that was brought out of the country by the provocative promises of other states, and in the strategic plan, to be able to reverse the processes by forming new creative elite. Sometimes a lifetime is not enough to overcome such an important and difficult task. However, Heydar Aliyev managed to organize this work masterfully. Our compatriots, whom he sent to the world's most prestigious educational institutions, participated actively in the establishment and development of the independent Azerbaijan, and intellectuals were prevented from leaving the country during his first leadership. Now this work is successfully continued by the followers of

Heydar Aliyev's policy. Dreams that are coming true every day make the spirit of the Great Leader happy.

Ilham Aliyev and Mrs. Mehriban Aliyeva continue to carry out the policies, ideas and thoughts that are waiting to be solved for the welfare of the people and the state, which were built on solid foundations by the National Leader Heydar Aliyev.

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Abbasov Namiq (Azərbaycan)

AZƏRBAYCAN MƏDƏNİYYƏTİNDƏ HEYDƏR ƏLİYEV FENOMENİ

Kulturologiya elmi Heydər Əliyev fenomenini öyrəndikcə, əslində, müstəqil Azərbaycan dövlətinin tarixi keçmişini, bu gününü, ölkəmizdə həyata keçirilən mədəni quruculuq prosesini öyrənir. Tarixi gerçəkliklərin müqayisəsi böyük şəxsiyyətlərin fəaliyyətinin qiymətləndirilməsində ən obyektiv istinad yeridir. Bu mənada, Ulu Öndər Heydər Əliyevin rəhbərlik etdiyi Azərbaycan istisnasız olaraq daimproblemlərin həllinə doğru irəliləyən, iqtisadi, sosial, humanitar və mədəni sahələrdə intibaha canatan, hər addımda insan və şəxsiyyət amilini uca tutan ölkə kimi görünür. Heydər Əliyev fenomeni – onun yaratdıqları – təzahür edən, aşkara çıxan mədəniyyət hadisələri Azərbaycan mədəniyyətinin mahiyyətini ifadə edir.

Açar sözlər: mədəni quruculuq, milli-mənəvi dəyərlər, idarəetmə mədəniyyəti, davamlı inkişaf, xalqa xidmət.

Аббасов Намик (Азербайджан)

ФЕНОМЕН ГЕЙДАРА АЛИЕВА В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЕ

В статье отмечается, что культурологическая наука, изучая феномен Гейдара Алиева, по сути, изучает прошлое, настоящее независимого Азербайджана, процесс культурного строительства в нашей стране. Сравнение исторических реалий – наиболее объективный ориентир для оценки творчества великих личностей. В этом смысле Азербайджан, которым руководил Великий Лидер Гейдар Алиев, видится страной, которая постоянно движется к решению проблем, стремится к возрождению в экономической, социальной, гуманитарной и культурной областях, ценит человеческий и личностный фактор. Феномен Гейдара Алиева, его созидательный труд выражают культурные явления, сущность культуры Азербайджана.

Ключевые слова: культурное строительство, национально-нравственные ценности, культура управления, устойчивое развитие, государственная служба.